

Measuring Species Richness of Mangrove Saplings in Matla Char of the Sunderbans

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Abstract

A lanceolate-shaped mid-channel bar can be seen forming soon after the construction of the bridge over the Matla River near the town of Canning. Within a few years, the mid-channel bar grows in length and width, but the height does not change much. But when vegetation appears after that mid channel bar, the height of the tidal bar gradually increases at a rapid rate. The vegetation settling on the mid channel bar are characteristically the seedlings of the mangrove species. The ten identified mangrove species grown in the tidal bar show species richness and relative diversity when the sampled data are computed using Shannon Wiener Index including other diversity indices.

Keywords: Matla, Mangroves, Species richness, Relative diversity, Shannon Wiener Index, Magurran Index, Margalef Index

Introduction

Forest is a very dynamic ecosystem and is almost changing with space and time (Shameem et al., 2010). The Sunderbans ecosystem is more dynamic as this ecosystem is controlled by biogeochemical cycles (Das, 2017). Sunderbans is a completely riverine area. Forests of mangroves cover the riverbanks, point bars, mid channel bars, and island region of the Sunderbans surrounded by river channels and tidal courses (Das, 2021). Sunderbans is the largest single mangrove forest in the world (Das, 2015). Tides flow here twice a day. The mangroves are almost submerged under the tidal water. Again, when the saline water recedes during low tide, this forest of mangroves exposes up. Mangroves are able to adapt to saline or brackish water and silty-clay muddy soil. The Indian Sunderbans has numerous tributaries which are interconnected and make a river network (Das, 2023). Among 31 river courses, tidal channels and inlets, the Matla River is one of the most important rivers in the Sunderbans. This Matla River is almost endangered due to human intervention.

The worst effects of damming the flowing river are seen in many areas of the Sunderbans. The Matla River is dying fast from damming the upper reaches of the river course. Even centuries ago, the Matla River was already disconnected from Hooghly River due to some changing events of regional geological set up and neo tectonism (Das 2011, 2011a, 2014). Recently, after the construction of a bridge over Matla River near Canning town in 2011, silt has accumulated in the riverbed of Matla and created a tidal shoal namely Matla Char. Today, seedlings grown from the seeds of mangroves drifted with the tide have shaped the tidal shoal of the accumulated sediments growing in the Matla riverbed

into an island. Due to the sediment trapping capacity of mangroves saplings, the island is rapidly accumulating sediment, and the island is rising fast. Most of the mangrove seedlings that have been identified in the emerging island in the riverbed of Matla belong to the list of Indian Sunderbans mangroves (figure 1). All the saplings are not only densely populated, but also abundant. The species richness and relative diversity of these mangrove saplings naturally grown in the Matla Char is the objective of the present study.

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Materials and Methods

Matla Char becomes completely inundated with tidal waters. So, geomorphic mapping and data collection are only possible during the ebb tide when water recedes completely from the Matla Char. Field mapping has been done with the clinometer compass, while mangrove saplings identified, and number of different species are sampled by counting from randomly selected transects on the mudflat of Matla Char along 23 cross sections. Species richness and relative diversity indices are determined by using the statistical formula of Shannon-Wiener diversity index, Margalef diversity index, and Magurran diversity index

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(Magurran, 1988, 2004; Margalef, 1958; Shannon and Weaver 1949).

Result and Discussion

Matla Char, emerging almost in the thalweg of the river, is elongated in shape, which is about 2782 m in length, and the maximum and minimum widths are 258.89 m and 42.34 m respectively, though Matla Char is not a continuous tidal bar. It is separated by a wide creek almost at the top of the tidal island dividing the Matla Char into two: northern and southern parts, of which the southern portion of the tidal bar is comparatively longer than the northern piece, and it is about 2.33 km (figure 2). The Matla Char is an ebb-tidal bar in nature and is almost covered with mangrove saplings. About eight mangrove species were identified during the survey in 23 transects which were randomly chosen. The average sampled data of the mangrove saplings collected from 23 cross sections is shown in Table 1. Species richness and relative diversity are determined from the sampled data applying the formulae of Shannon Wiener Index, Magurran Index, and Margalef Index (Das 2021, a). The result shows species richness of the mangrove saplings which are abundantly occurring in the Matla Char indicating a unique combination of mangroves that might control the mangrove ecosystems in Matla Char in near future.

The estimated Shannon-Wiener's index is 2.071989906 and the value of $\exp(2.071989906)$ is 7.94, that indicates the community with Shannon-Wiener index of 2.071989906 has an equivalent diversity as a community with about 8 equally common mangrove species (Table 1). And these 8 equally common mangrove species are *Avicennia marina*, *Avicennia alba*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Avicennia officinalis*, *Ceriops decandra*, *Sonneratia apetala*, *Xylocarpus granatum*, and *Acanthus ilicifolius* identified in the mudflat of Matla Char of the Sunderbans.

Considering the value of Shannon-Wiener's index 2.071989906, evenness (E) or relative diversity is calculated. Evenness shows a relevant value which is 0.899853783. The value 0.899853783 reveals the relative diversity of ten mangrove species identified in the mudflat of Matla Char of the Sunderbans. An evenness (E) value so close to 1 indicates that the different species are indeed evenly spread out throughout the sampled area, or in other terms, the species are equally distributed over the Matla Char. The Margalef Diversity Index is calculated using the statistical formula and shows the diversity index value is 1.642144306 that indicates evenness of all the mangrove species grown in the mudflat of Matla Char. The value of the calculated Magurran Index is 0.645497224 which indicates the species richness of the mangrove species grown in the Matla Char (Table 1).

Figure 1. Abundant occurrence of *Avicennia* sp. and *Acanthus ilicifolius* on the mudflat of Matla Char. Note *Suaeda nudiflora*, a mangrove associated herbaceous plant appeared in huge numbers.

Table 1. Calculation of Shannon Wiener Index and Diversity Index.

Local Names	Scientific Names	Number of each species	H'	D
JeleGaran	<i>Ceriopsdecandra</i>	18	0.194270037	0.005334728
Mat Garan	<i>Ceriops tagal</i>	7	0.103096256	0.000732218
Peyara Bain	<i>Avicennia alba</i>	39	0.295275058	0.02583682
Kal Bain	<i>Avicennia marina</i>	61	0.348148619	0.063807531
Bain	<i>Avicennia officinalis</i>	17	0.187525979	0.00474198
Keora	<i>Sonneratia apetala</i>	12	0.149786614	0.002301255
Chak- Keora	<i>Sonneratiacaseolaris</i>	8	0.113373246	0.00097629
Geoan	<i>Excoecariaagallocha</i>	36	0.284567998	0.021966527
Dhundhul	<i>Xylocarpus granatum</i>	9	0.123128038	0.00125523
Hargoz	<i>Acanthus ilicifolius</i>	33	0.272818062	0.01841004
	S=10	N=240	H' = 2.071989906	D = 0.854637378

Figure 2. A diagrammatic sketch of Matla Char showing transects of survey and sampling along the tidal bar.

Conclusion

A very dense presence of mangrove saplings grown naturally on Matla Char can be observed. Due to the dense presence of saplings, sand, silt, and clay carried by the river water during high tide from the estuarine region are deposited on the Matla Char at a rapid rate. The survey shows that Matla Island has risen by about 40 cm in just one year. Moreover, the relevant arrangement of the saplings of the mangrove species subsequently resulted in dense forests and an enriched mangrove succession in the near future that will lead to a highly dynamic mangroves ecosystem. The computed values of Shannon Wiener Index in this present study related to the mangroves saplings generation in comparison to the elevation of the riverbed of Matla not only reflect the positive result but also show the species richness including the relative diversity of the grown-up species. Apart from the Shannon-Wiener Index, Magurran, and Margalef indices also support the relative diversity of the mangrove species which is positively correlated with the ecological environments of Matla Char of the Sunderbans.

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